

Supplementary Material for

**Field Investigation of Boat-Generated Wave
Dynamics
and Their Role in Riverbank Erosion**

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Nomenclature

Roman Symbols

H_s	Significant wave height [m]
V_B	Speed of the boat in field/laboratory tests [km h^{-1}]
X_B	Distance of the sailing line from the riverbank [m]

1 Introduction

This supplementary material provides additional figures supporting the field investigation of boat-generated wave dynamics and their role in riverbank erosion along the Rideau River. The figures present additional results for the tested recreational boats and show the effects of boat speed, sailing-line distance from the riverbank, and movement direction on the measured wave heights.

2 Field Investigations on Boat-Induced Bank Erosion: Campaigns of 2023 and 2024

3 Jet ski – Field Test on 2023-09-13

3.1 The Effect of Boat Speed on Significant Wave Height

Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the effect of boat speed (V_B) on significant wave height (H_s) at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively. In these Figures, X_B is the distance of the sailing line from the riverbank.

Figure 1: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: jet ski).

Figure 2: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: jet ski).

3.2 The Effect of Boat Sailing-Line Distance from the Riverbank on Significant Wave Height

Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the effect of **boat sailing-line** distance from the riverbank on H_s at different boat speeds when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 3: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: jet ski).

Figure 4: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: jet ski).

3.3 The Effect of Boat Movement Direction on Significant Wave Height

Figure 5 shows the effect of movement direction on H_s .

Figure 5: Effect of boat movement direction on H_s (Boat type: jet ski).

4 Water Ski Boat – Field Test on 2023-09-20

4.1 The Effect of Boat Speed on Significant Wave Height

Figures 6 and 7 illustrate the effect of boat speed on significant wave height (H_s) at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 6: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: water ski boat).

Figure 7: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: water ski boat).

4.2 The Effect of Boat Sailing-Line Distance from the Riverbank on Significant Wave Height

Figures 8 and 9 illustrate the effect of **boat sailing-line** distance from the riverbank on H_s at different boat speeds when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 8: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: water ski boat).

Figure 9: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: water ski boat).

4.3 The Effect of Boat Movement Direction on Significant Wave Height

Figure 10 shows the effect of movement direction on H_s .

Figure 10: Effect of boat movement direction on H_s (Boat type: water ski boat).

5 Fishing Boat – Field Test on 2023-09-27

5.1 The Effect of Boat Speed on Significant Wave Height

Figures 11 and 12 illustrate the effect of boat speed on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 11: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: fishing boat).

Figure 12: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: fishing boat).

5.2 The Effect of Boat Sailing-Line Distance from the Riverbank on Significant Wave Height

Figures 13 and 14 illustrate the effect of boat sailing-line distance from the riverbank on H_s at different boat speeds when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 13: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: fishing boat).

Figure 14: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: fishing boat).

5.3 The Effect of Boat Movement Direction on Significant Wave Height

Figure 15 shows the effect of movement direction on H_s .

Figure 15: Effect of boat movement direction on H_s (Boat type: fishing boat).

6 Fishing Boat – Field Test on 2023-10-04

6.1 The Effect of Boat Speed on Significant Wave Height

Figures 16 and 17 illustrate the effect of boat speed on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 16: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: fishing boat).

Figure 17: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: fishing boat).

6.2 The Effect of Boat Sailing-Line Distance from the Riverbank on Significant Wave Height

Figures 18 and 19 illustrate the effect of boat sailing-line distance from the riverbank on H_s at different boat speeds when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 18: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: fishing boat).

Figure 19: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: fishing boat).

6.3 The Effect of Boat Movement Direction on Significant Wave Height

Figure 20 shows the effect of movement direction on H_s .

Figure 20: Effect of boat movement direction on H_s (Boat type: fishing boat).

7 Wake Boat with the Wake Shaper on – Field Test on 2024-09-25

7.1 The Effect of Boat Speed on Significant Wave Height

Figures 21 and 22 illustrate the effect of boat speed on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 21: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: wake boat with the wake shaper on).

Figure 22: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: wake boat with the wake shaper on).

7.2 The Effect of Boat Sailing-Line Distance from the Riverbank on Significant Wave Height

Figures 23 and 24 illustrate the effect of boat sailing-line distance from the riverbank on H_s at different boat speeds when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 23: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: wake boat with the wake shaper on).

Figure 24: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: wake boat with the wake shaper on).

7.3 The Effect of Boat Movement Direction on Significant Wave Height

Figure 25 shows the effect of movement direction on H_s .

Figure 25: Effect of boat movement direction on H_s (Boat type: wake boat with the wake shaper on).

8 Wake Boat with the Wake Shaper off – Field Test on 2024-09-25

8.1 The Effect of Boat Speed on Significant Wave Height

Figures 26 and 27 illustrate the effect of boat speed on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 26: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: wake boat with the wake shaper off).

Figure 27: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: wake boat with the wake shaper off).

8.2 The Effect of Boat Sailing-Line Distance from the Riverbank on Significant Wave Height

Figures 28 and 29 illustrate the effect of boat sailing-line distance from the riverbank on H_s at different boat speeds when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 28: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: wake boat with the wake shaper off).

Figure 29: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: wake boat with the wake shaper off).

8.3 The Effect of Boat Movement Direction on Significant Wave Height

Figure 30 shows the effect of movement direction on H_s .

Figure 30: Effect of boat movement direction on H_s (Boat type: wake boat with the wake shaper off).

9 Sea Ray SLX 280 – Field Test on 2024-10-04

9.1 The Effect of Boat Speed on Significant Wave Height

Figures 31 and 32 illustrate the effect of boat speed on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 31: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: Sea Ray SLX 280).

Figure 32: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: Sea Ray SLX 280).

9.2 The Effect of Boat Sailing-Line Distance from the Riverbank on Significant Wave Height

Figures 33 and 34 illustrate the effect of boat sailing-line distance from the riverbank on H_s at different boat speeds when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 33: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: Sea Ray SLX 280).

Figure 34: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: Sea Ray SLX 280).

9.3 The Effect of Boat Movement Direction on Significant Wave Height

Figure 35 shows the effect of movement direction on H_s .

Figure 35: Effect of boat movement direction on H_s (Boat type: Sea Ray SLX 280).

10 Bass Boat – Field Test on 2024-10-09

10.1 The Effect of Boat Speed on Significant Wave Height

Figures 36 and 37 illustrate the effect of boat speed on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 36: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: bass boat).

Figure 37: Effect of V_B on H_s at different distances from the riverbank when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: bass boat).

10.2 The Effect of Boat Sailing-Line Distance from the Riverbank on Significant Wave Height

Figures 38 and 39 illustrate the effect of boat sailing-line distance from the riverbank on H_s at different boat speeds when the boat moves in the upstream and downstream directions, respectively.

Figure 38: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the upstream direction (Boat type: bass boat).

Figure 39: Effect of X_B on H_s at different speeds when the boat moves in the downstream direction (Boat type: bass boat).

10.3 The Effect of Boat Movement Direction on Significant Wave Height

Figure 40 shows the effect of movement direction on H_s .

Figure 40: Effect of boat movement direction on H_s (Boat type: bass boat).